

Immunostaining of U937 PMA-differentiated macrophages

Objective:

Describe in detail the procedure for immunostaining technique using U937 cell line.

Method

1. Obtain a full differentiated cell culture (U937 PMA-differentiated macrophages).

2. **Cell fixation:** add 200 µl/well of 4% PFA. Incubate at room temperature for 10 min at room temperature. Then, discard it.

3. Wash one with 200 µl of PBS. Add 200 µl of PBS/well.

IMPORTANT! Store the samples cover from the light at 4 C.

4. **Cell permeabilization:** add 200 µl/well of PermQuench buffer (2% (w/v) BSA and 0,02% saponin in PBS) for 30 minutes at room temperature.

5. Wash three times the cells with 200 µl/ well of PBS for 30 sec at room temperature.

6. Primary antibody (X):

6.1. Prepare a dilution 1:300 of **X primary antibody**. For dilution, use PermQuench buffer (2% (w/v) BSA and 0,02% saponin in PBS).

6.2. Add 150 µl/ well of **anti-X solution**. Incubate for 2 h at room temperature.

7. Wash three times the cells with 200 µl/well of PBS for 30 sec at room temperature.

8. Secondary antibody (Y):

8.1. Dilute under sterile conditions a **solution of secondary antibody -Alexa** (1:500 dilution). For dilution, use PermQuench buffer (2% (w/v) BSA and 0,02% saponin in PBS)

8.2. Add 150 µl/well of the solution obtained in **step 10.1** and incubate at room temperature for 2 h. **Keep the plate covered from the light.**

8.3 Wash five times the cells with 200 µl/well of PBS for 30 sec at room temperature.

9. Wash three times the cells with 250 µl/well of PBS for 30 sec at room temperature.

10. Nuclear Staining (optional)

10.1. Dilute 2 drops of Nuclei stain in 1mL of PermQuench buffer (2% (w/v) BSA and 0,02% saponin in PBS)

10.2. Add 200 µl/coverlip of the Nuclei stain solution and incubate for 10 min at room temperature.

11. Prepare the slide for confocal/fluorescence microscopy.

13. Storage of samples: ALWAYS keep your samples with PBS!